

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

COHERENT SYNCHRONIZATION OF REACTIONS OF 2-PICOLINE OXIDATION BY HYDROGEN PEROXIDE AND NITROUS OXIDE

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Abstract

The paper reports the homogeneous transformation of 2-picoline by thermal decomposition of nitric oxide (1). The reaction was carried out in the gas phase, at relatively low temperatures, atmospheric pressure. The reaction mechanism of dealkodimerization and dehydrodimerization of 2-picoline by aqueous solution of hydrogen peroxide and nitric oxide (1), respectively, whose participation leads to selective obtaining of target products used in many industries, was considered. On specific examples, in particular, oxidation of 2-picoline by "green oxidants"- H_2O_2 and N_2O with the help of the determinant equation, the potentialities of the reaction media are estimated and the type of chemical interaction is shown. The most probable reaction mechanism is proposed.

Keywords: 2-picoline, oxidation, dealkodimerization, dehydrodimerization, coherently synchronized, determinant equation.

In recent years, organic synthetic chemists have shown great interest in compounds with heteroatoms. It has become obvious that nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds are of particular interest (by their structure as well as chemical properties). It should be added that of particular interest is pyridine and its derivatives, i.e., having in their composition, in addition to the carbon atom, a nitrogen atom. This gives these compounds a number of special properties. There are special forms of pyridine bases (dipyridyls), which form a stable complex with a number of metals (in particular, the ruthenium complex is widely studied) catalyzing the photodegradation of water into hydrogen and oxygen [1,2]. One can cite many numbers of pyridine bases that have found application in the production of pharmaceuticals [3,4]. Therefore, the development of theoretical and experimental bases for the oxidation of N-substituted heterocyclic compounds (in particular, 2-picoline) by hydrogen peroxide and nitrous oxide in the coherent synchronization mode is of interest because these reactions yield compounds with high selectivity required in the petrochemical, chemical, and pharmaceutical industries.

Results and discussion

The present communication shows how by oxidation of 2-picoline (2-P) with the "green oxidants"- H_2O_2 and N_2O , practically important compounds with high selectivity can be obtained. 2-P oxidation reactions were carried out in a quartz flow-type reactor. The design of the reactor ensures the introduction of oxidant vapour (H_2O_2 or N_2O) into the reaction zone through a quartz tube in undecomposed form. Through another quartz tube, i.e. separately from the oxidizer, the initial oxidizable substance (2-P) preheated in gaseous state is fed into the reactor. The quench zone, which follows the reaction zone, is located as close to it as possible. This quenching system is used in order to prevent oxidation of the reaction products outside the reaction zone from developing. Quantitative and qualitative determination of the obtained reaction products was carried out by chromatography (oxidation of 2-P with hydrogen peroxide) and chromatomass spectroscopy (oxidation of 2-P with nitrous oxide).

Studies of the reaction of dealkodimerization of 2-P by aqueous hydrogen peroxide solution showed that the reaction proceeds according to a simplified technology and with a relatively high yield. As a result of experiments in the temperature range of 650-725°C it was

found that the main product is 2,2-dipyridyl (2,2-DP). Dealkodimerization of 2-P by hydrogen peroxide was studied in a wide range of variation of process parameters (feed rate of 2-P, volume ratio 2-P:H₂O₂, temperature, concentration of aqueous hydrogen peroxide solution). Under these conditions, 2,2-DP was obtained from 2-P, bypassing the pyridine formation stage, with a yield of 52 wt.% [5,6]. In this case, synchronization of reactions of hydrogen peroxide decomposition and dealkodimerization of 2-P makes it possible to carry out in the mode of their interaction with each other (mutual strengthening and weakening - chemical interference) and easily enough to regulate the rate of these reactions. It should be noted that in this reaction system, a mandatory condition for the realization of chemical interference is its quantitative characteristic, defined by the determinant equation [6]. Thus, the found value of $D=0.17$ (the optimal condition for dealkodimerization of 2-P), according to the chemical interference scale [7-9], is in the region of chemical conjugation, since we know that in the limit for coherently synchronized reactions $D \rightarrow 1$. Thus, the kinetics of the 2-P dealkodimerization reaction, coherently synchronized with the hydrogen peroxide decomposition reaction, was studied and a probable mechanism for this reaction was proposed.

The oxidation of 2-P by nitrous oxide in the gas phase is undoubtedly of considerable theoretical and applied interest. For this purpose, it was interesting to study and show the principal possibility of the oxidation reaction of 2-P by nitrous oxide and to show the chemical conjugation of two reactions (thermal decomposition of nitrous oxide and oxidation of 2-P) occurring in this reaction system. In order to solve the question about the principal possibility of realization of chemical conjugation in this reaction medium, it is necessary to find the kinetic conditions under which such a system will work. This requires experimental studies. For this purpose, the reaction of coherently synchronized oxidation of 2-P by nitrous oxide was studied in a wide range of variation of process parameters (feed rates of 2-P and N₂O, temperature).

As a result of the conducted studies, optimal conditions were established under which 2,2-ethylenedipyridine (2,2-EDP) is mainly formed with a yield of 31.0 wt.%. The kinetic studies conducted made it possible to assume that nitrous oxide, thermally decomposing into end products: nitrogen and molecular oxygen, generates a highly active intermediate in the system – atomic oxygen, which is consumed in the secondary oxidation reaction of 2-P (chemical conjugation). The formed active center - atomic oxygen, during thermal decomposition of nitrous oxide is consumed in volume by interaction with 2-P, resulting in the formation of -OH, which continues the chain leading to the production of atomic oxygen again, etc.

Using the determinant equation [6], a quantitative assessment of the inducing effect of the primary reaction on the secondary, main reaction is given, where the values of D are in the range of 0.54. According to the chemical interference determinant scale [10], this value is in the region of chemical conjugation, when the pri-

mary reaction (N₂O decomposition) induces a secondary one – dehydrodimerization of 2-P. Thus, considering the reactions of 2-P oxidation by hydrogen peroxide and nitrous oxide (decomposition of H₂O₂ and N₂O - catalase reactions), it can be seen that the fulfillment of the coherence condition of chemical interference [10].

Conclusion

This work is devoted to the search for new, highly efficient ways to obtain practically important nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds based on 2-P.

The application of hydrogen peroxide and nitrous oxide allowed to carry out the following processes under simplified technology under homogeneous conditions: dealkodimerization and dehydrodimerization of 2-P, the implementation of which in catalytic processes present certain difficulties. On the basis of the above studied processes, the high efficiency of hydrogen peroxide and nitrous oxide as “green oxidants” was shown, with the help of which practical important products with high yields and relatively high selectivity were synthesized.

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